

PHILOSOPHICAL-ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS OF CONFLICT OF INTEREST AND PREVENTION OF CORRUPT RELATIONS

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Аннотация: В данной статье представлен аналитический анализ четкого и последовательного определения плана мероприятий по предотвращению и устранению конфликта интересов при формировании коррупционной безопасности в обществе. Предупреждение возникновения коррупционных отношений, в то же время возможность борьбы с созданием условий, которые могут негативно сказаться на экономической стабильности, привести к нерациональному и нецелевому расходованию средств государственного бюджета на основе различных цепных коррупционных отношений с учетом.

Ключевые слова: коррупция, защита от коррупции, коррупционное отношение, государство, закон, взяточничество, экономическая стабильность, честность, конфликт интересов.

Annotation: This article presents an analytical analysis of clearly and consistently defining a plan of measures to prevent and eliminate conflicts of interest in the formation of corruption security in society. Preventing the

occurrence of corrupt relations, at the same time, the ability to fight against the creation of conditions that can have a negative impact on economic stability, lead to misdirection and improper spending of the state budget on the basis of various chain corrupt relations given.

Keywords: *corruption, safety from corruption, corrupt attitude, state, law, bribery, economic stability, honesty, conflict of interest.*

Jamiyatning yangi taraqqiyot bosqichida korrupsiyaga qarshi kurash yangi bosqichga olib chiqildi. Ayniqsa, O‘zbekistonning yangi taraqqiyot strategiyasida korrupsiyaga qarshi murosasizlikni shakllantirish, davlat miqiyosida kuchli kurash mexanizmlarini yaratish, jamiyatda jamoatchilik monitoringini takomillashtirishga qaratilgan bir qancha ishlar yo‘lga qo‘yilmoqda. Zero, «yangi O‘zbekiston strategiyasi korrupsiyadan holi mamlakat barpo etishni nazarda tutadi. Ushbu maqsad bugun butun jamiyatimizni jipslashtiruvchi omilga aylanmoqda. Korrupsiya balosini jamiyatimiz hayotidan yo‘q qilishga qaratilgan siyosat kelgusida ham qat’iy davom ettiriladi»¹. «Jamiyatimizda korrupsiya, turli jinoyatlarni sodir etish va boshqa huquqbuzarlik holatlariga qarshi kurashish, ularga yo‘l qo‘ymaslik, jinoyatga jazo albatta muqarrar ekani to‘g‘risidagi qonun talablarini amalda ta‘minlash bo‘yicha qat’iy choralar ko‘rishimiz zarur.»² Shuningdek, korrupsiyaviy munosabatlarning ochiq-oydin tan olinishi, xalqaro tashkilotlar tomonidan baholangan vaziyatni to‘g‘rilash uchun davlat siyosati darajasida chora-tadbirlarning belgilanayotganligi e’tirofga sazovordir. Jumladan, «Bu borada Korrupsiyaga oid jinoyatlarni sodir etishda aybdor deb topilgan shaxslarning ochiq elektron reestri»ning yuritilishi, «Davlat xizmatchilarining daromadlari va mol-mulkini deklaratsiya qilish to‘g‘risida»gi qonun qabul qilinishi olib borayotgan sa’y-harakatlarimizning samarasini oshirishga xizmat

¹Mirziyoev Sh.M. Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasi. –T.: O‘zbekiston. 2022. – 428-430 b.

² Mirziyoev Sh.M. Erkin va farovon, demokratik o‘zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. –T.: O‘zbekiston. 2016. – 10 b.

qiladi. «Korrupsiyani qabul qilish indeksi» reytingida mamlakatimizning egallayotgan o‘rinlari bu boradagi harakatlarimizni baholovchi asosiy ko‘rsatkichlar sirasiga kiradi»³. Bu esa, korrupsion xavfsizlikni shakllantirishda nimalarga e‘tibor qaratish, qanday kurash usullarini ishlab chiqish, jazolash mexanizmlarini yaratish borasida rivojlangan davlatlar tajribasi asosida aniq chora-tadbirlar rejasini ishlab chiqishga imkon beradi.

Bugungi kunda jamiyatda korrupsiya xavfsizligini shakllantirishda manfaatlar to‘qnashuvini oldini olish va uni bartaraf etishga doir chora-tadbirlar rejasini ham aniq va izchillikda belgilab olishni talab etmoqda. Bu orqali korrupsiyaviy munosabatlarni yuzaga kelishini oldini olish mumkin bo‘ladi, shu bilan birga turli zanjirli korrupsiyaviy munosabatlar asosida iqtisodiy barqarorlikka salbiy ta‘sir o‘tkaza oladigan, davlat byudjetini noto‘g‘ri yo‘lantirilishiga, noto‘g‘ri sarflanishiga olib keladigan sharoitni yaratilishiga qarshi kurashish mumkin bo‘ladi.

«Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurash to‘g‘risida»gi qonunga ko‘ra, manfaatlar to‘qnashuvini oldini olish uchun «davlat organlarining davlat xizmatchilari mansab yoki xizmat majburiyatlarini bajarish chog‘ida manfaatlar to‘qnashuviga olib keladigan yoki olib kelishi mumkin bo‘lgan shaxsiy manfaatdorlikka yo‘l qo‘ymasligi»⁴ kerakligi aniq belgilangan. Bu esa, davlat organlari davlat xizmatchilari, mansabdor shaxslar faoliyatini tartibga solish zaruratini ham keltirib chiqaradi. Unga ko‘ra, mansabdor shaxslarni turli sohalarda tadbirkorlik faoliyati bilan shug‘ullanishini cheklash, yoki yaqin qarindoshlarini tadbirkorlik faoliyati bilan shug‘ullanishiga doir aniq qoidalarni ham ishlab chiqishni talab etadi. Mazkur qonunga ko‘ra, davlat organlari davlat xizmatchilari yoki mansabdor shaxslar faoliyatida «manfaatlar to‘qnashuvi yuzaga kelgan taqdirda, bevosita rahbarni darhol xabardor qilishi kerak. Manfaatlar to‘qnashuvi

³Mirziyoev Sh.M. Yangi O‘zbekiston taraqqiyot strategiyasi. –T.: O‘zbekiston. 2022. – 433 b

⁴O‘zbekiston Respublikasining «Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashish to‘g‘risida»gi Qonuni. 2017. 4 yanvar// <http://parlament.gov.uz/uz/laws/adopted/253/19165>

mavjudligi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar olgan rahbar bu to'qnashuvning oldini olish yoki uni bartaraf etish yuzasidan o'z vaqtida choralar ko'rishi shart»ligi belgilangan bo'lsada, bu qoida bajarilmaganda qanday huquqbuzarliklar sodir bo'lishi, qanday jazo qo'llanishi aniq belgilab qo'yilmagan. Shuning uchun korrupsiya xavfsizligini shakllantirishda manfaatlar to'qnashuvi holati kuzatilishi mansabdor shaxs faoliyatini so'roq ostida qoldiradigan darajada munosabatga tortilsa, jamoatchilik monitoringini bunday holatlarda yuqori mas'uliyat bilan ishlasa maqsadga muvofiq bo'lardi.

Manfaatlar to'qnashuvi tushunchasini quyidagicha tariflash mumkin. Davlat tashkiloti xodimining, uning yaqin qarindoshlarining va unga aloqador shaxslarning shaxsiy manfaatlari bilan fuqarolarning, tashkilotning yoki davlatning huquqlari va qonuniy manfaatlari o'rtasida qarama-qarshilik yuzaga kelgan va kelayotgan (mavjud manfaatlar to'qnashuvi) yoxud yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan (taxmin qilinayotgan manfaatlar to'qnashuvi) vaziyatga nisbatan manfaatlar to'qnashuvi ishlatiladi. Demak, manfaatlar to'qnashuvi deganda shaxsiy manfaatdorlik tashkilot xodimining mansab yoki xizmat majburiyatlarini lozim darajada bajarishiga ta'sir ko'rsatayotgan yoki ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin bo'lgan hamda shaxsiy manfaatdorlik bilan tashkilotning huquqlari va qonuniy manfaatlari o'rtasida qarama-qarshilik yuzaga kelayotgan yoki yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan vaziyat tushuniladi.

Iqtisodiy erkinlik, iqtisodiy demokratiya to'g'risida gap ketgan zahoti AQShlik siyosatshunos Robert Dalni esga olishadi va uning «plyuralistik demokratiya» g'oyasiga murojaat qilishadi. Uning ilmiy g'oyasiga ko'ra, tenglik har doim erkinlikka, iqtisodiy demokratiya har doim siyosiy demokratiyaning rivojlanishiga olib kelavermaydi. Sanoatning rivojlanishi, mulkiy plyuralizmning rang-baranglashuvi «siyosiy hayotda foydalanadigan resurslarga teng ega bo'lmagan fuqarolar korrupsiyani shakllanishiga olib keldi»⁵. Siyosiy hayotda

⁵Dal R. Vvedenie v ekonomicheskuyu demokratiyu. Per. s angl. –M.: Nauka; SP IKPA, 1991. 15 s.

faol qatnashishini ta'minlaydigan resurslarga (mulkka, mavqega va b.) ega bo'lmashlik kishilarning ijtimoiy-siyosiy hayotga ta'sirini susaytiradi, hatto siyosiy demokratiyani fiksiyaga aylantiradi. Bu o'rinda AQSh prezidentligiga, mer lavozimlariga mudom yirik mulk egalari, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy hayotda yuqori mavqega ega bo'lgan shaxslar da'vogar bo'lib kelganini eslash o'rinlidir. Demak, iqtisodiy demokratiya hamma vaqt ham siyosiy demokratiyaga xizmat qilavermas va jamiyatda tenglik, adolat tamoyillarining qaror topishiga xizmat qilavermas ekan.

Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurash agentligi rahbari A.Burxonov fikricha, «so'nggi yillarda davlat organlari faoliyati ochiqligi va shaffofligini ta'minlash mexanizmlari, shuningdek, jamoatchilik nazorati institutlari tubdan takomillashtirildi. Raqamli va onlayn texnologiyalarning keng qo'llanilishi davlat organlarining jamiyat oldidagi hisobdorligini oshirdi. Yer uchastkalari va davlat aktivlarini, shuningdek, avtotransport vositalari uchun davlat raqam belgilarini onlayn auksionda sotish tizimi yo'lga qo'yildi hamda doimiy takomillashtirilib borilmoqda»⁶. Mana shunday tashkiliy masalalarni yangicha munosabat asosida hal etilishi ham jamiyatda korrupsiyaviy munosabatlarga bo'lgan fikrlash tarzini tubdan o'zgartirdi. Shu bilan birga davlat xizmatlarini raqamlashtirilishi va inson omilini chiqarib tashlanishi ham o'z samarasini ko'rsata boshladi.

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⁶Korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashish umummilliy birdamlikni talab etadi.
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